

Functional Form of Entropy Due to Physical Constraints? Part 2

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Given a statistical/probabilistic problem, one may write a priori constraints. Two common constraints are: $\sum_i p(e_i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)=E_{ave}$. These allow for multiple $p(e_i)$ sets as solutions and so an approach is required to choose a unique $p(e_i)$ set, presumably one with the least amount of information. In Part 1, we argued that the minimal amount of information implied that e_i is only linked to $h(p(e_i))=-e_i/T$. In other words, given a reaction, there is no special energy information except that linked to $p(e_i)$. This turns out to be equivalent to $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$ ((A)) for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. In such a case, as shown in Part 1, one may create the function: $\sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ and argue that $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i)+dp(e_i)$ leads to expressions which are a linear combination of the differentials of the constraints. (Such an approach may be used for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and for the Tsallis case with $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i \rightarrow \sum_i p(e_i) e_i^q$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i)) \rightarrow \sum_i p(e_i) e_i^q h(p(e_i))$).

In some cases, ((A)) does not hold, but one may still wish to have a lack of knowledge linked with all e_i, e_j pairs with the same sum. Physically, this may be associated with reactions which are based on more than $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ as in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases. Thus, we suggest a dual space with $g(p(e_i))$ replacing $p(e_i)$. In such a case, one may introduce an extremization process using $\sum_i g(p(e_i)) F(g(p(e_i)))$ subject to $\sum_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number}_1$ and $\sum_i e_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number}_2$. This approach yields the correct result (with $g(p(e_i))$ known, but differs from the usual entropy maximization (using $d/dp(e_i)$) subject to the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$.

Simple Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Case and Differentials of Constraints

A priori constraints are important as they are readily observed in a statistical system. For example, two common constraints are:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E_{ave} \quad ((1))$$

Many sets of $\{ p(e_i) \}$ satisfy ((1)) and one seeks a unique set. The question is: On what should this unique set be based? We suggest it should be linked to information, where the word is taken to mean more than simply $\ln(p(e_i))$ as in information science. We show, however, that in the simple MB case, it does become $\ln(p(e_i))$.

We argue that the key physical quantity in the a priori constraints ((1)) is e_i , as the first constraint holds in all cases. The question then becomes: What is the influence of e_i on the system? One might argue that in elastic collisions it is linked with:

$$e_1+e_2= e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2))$$

If that is its only role, then one may link $p(e_i)$ (the probability for a particle to have e_i) with collisions represented by ((2)). In such a case, one has from reaction balance:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j) \text{ for any } e_i+e_j = e_1+e_2 \quad ((3))$$

((3)) then leads directly to the MB distribution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, using ((1)) to fix C and T .

An alternative approach is to create an information function:

$$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((3))$$

In the simplest case, $h(p(e_i))$ is the inverse function of $p(e_i)$, but there exist more complicated situations. Considering the simple case here, one may define:

Sum over i $p(e_i) h(p(e_i)) = \text{entropy} = \text{function which captures all of the physical } e_i \text{ information, either through a function of } e_i \text{ or } p(e_i) \text{ in a problem.}$

In the simplest case, $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ i.e $h(p(e_i))$ is the inverse of $p(e_i)$.

Next, one may set: $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i)+dp(e_i)$ ((4))

and argue that any changes are captured by a linear combination of the differentials of the constraints, i.e.

$$dp(e_i) h(p(e_i)) \rightarrow -e_i/T dp(e_i) \text{ so } h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((5a))$$

$$p(e_i) dh(p(e_i))/dp(e_i) = 1 \text{ or } h(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ so } p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((5b))$$

There are physical scenarios, however, which still have the constraints ((1)), but in which e_i or $p(e_i)$ plays a more complicated role than in ((3)). We thus want to generalize the above ideas to these situations. We consider three specific cases, the Fermi-Dirac scenario, the Bose-Einstein and a proposed MB replacement by a gamma function suggested in (1).

What Does Maximization Really Mean in the MB Case?

The idea of maximization implies one choose a stationary solution (which is a maximum), but what specifically is this solution? We note that ((3)) represents a unique solution which minimizes information (maximizes a lack of information). Thus, we suggest that it is the condition of having equal product probability for e_i, e_j pairs such that $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$ that is really represented by the maximization. In other words, this is the key statistical idea, i.e. a very specific form of information is bypassed.

The Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Cases

We first consider the Fermi-Dirac scenario which does not allow a particle to scatter into an energy level which has a particle present. (We ignore spin.). On average, this means:

$$p(e_1) (1-p(e_3)) p(e_2) (1-p(e_4)) = p(e_3) (1-p(e_1)) p(e_4) (1-p(e_2)) \quad ((6))$$

In other words, the role of $p(e_i)$ in the MB case ((3)) is replaced with $p(e_i) / (1-p(e_i))$ ((7))

As a result, one has from ((6)) and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$: $\ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ ((8))

One may solve for the FD distribution directly from ((8)), suggesting that one does not need to use a maximization of entropy subject to constraints process. Likewise, in the MB case, one may directly use ((2)) (reaction balance). The unique solution of reaction balance, however, represents a minimal amount of information and so should correspond to the result of a maximization process in the MB case. Even though $p(e_i)$ does not satisfy ((2)), $p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i)) = g(p(e_i))$ satisfies a similar condition.

We suggest that one may construct a dual space in which $p(e_i)$ is replaced with $g(p(e_i))$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = e_{ave}$ with $\sum_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number 1}$ and $\sum_i e_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number 2}$. One may then apply maximization to:

$\sum_i g(p(e_i)) F(g(p(e_i)))$ where $F(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ ((9)) so

$$dg F(g) = -e_i/T dg \quad \text{and} \quad g dF/dg = 1$$

Formally, one then obtains: $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ which yields the FD distribution ((10)).

We note the link to the differentials of the constraints, i.e.

$$\sum_i e_i dg(p(e_i)) = \sum_i e_i dg/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i dg(p(e_i)) = \sum_i dg/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) \quad ((11))$$

For the extremization in the dual space, one has: $dg(p(e_i))/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) F(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$
 $dg(p(e_i))/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) \quad \quad \quad ((12a))$

$$\text{and} \quad g(p(e_i)) dF/dg(p(e_i)) dg/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) = dg/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) \quad ((12b))$$

If one multiplies both sides of ((12a)) and ((12b)) by dp/dg then:

$$dp(e_i) F(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T dp(e_i) \quad \text{and} \quad g(p(e_i)) dF/dg dp(e_i) = 1 dp(e_i) \quad ((13))$$

Thus, there is a link, but one really extremizes in the dual space, we argue, to obtain a result consistent with e_i, e_j pairs (with the same sum) having the same product of $g(p(e_i))$'s result. The Bose-Einstein case follows with the minus sign in ((7)) changed to a plus.

Connection with Usual Entropy

The usual approach related to entropy is to create a function of $p(e_i)$ such that variation with respect to the function $p(e_i)$ together with constraints (brought in with Lagrange multipliers) yields 0. In the FD case:

$$p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) - (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i)) \text{ subject to } \sum e_i p(e_i) = A \text{ and } \sum p(e_i) = B \quad ((14))$$

One may see that this does not use a dual space approach, but yields the same distribution. For the BE case, one replaces the minus sign with a plus. We suggest that the dual space perhaps shows more clearly the equal weight (through $g(p(e_i))$ products) for any e_i, e_j pair with the same sum.

Replacing the MB Distribution with a Gamma Function

In (1), it is suggested that one replace the MB $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ with:

$$p(e_i) = C_1 (e_i/T)^{k-1} \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((15))$$

One may see that ((2)) is violated, but:

$p(e_i)/(e_i/T)^{k-1}$ substituted for $p(e_i)$ restores a ((2))-like expression. Thus, one could use:

$g(p(e_i), e_i) = p(e_i)/(e_i/T)^{k-1}$ and perform a maximization in dual space using this function

assuming that $d \sum_i g(p(e_i)) F(g(p(e_i)))$ is a linear combination of $d \sum_i g(p(e_i))$ and $d \sum_i e_i g(p(e_i))$ with $F(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$.

We suggest that in these above cases, the main idea behind maximization is to ensure that all e_i, e_j pairs carry the same product probability of some $g(p(e_i), e_i)$ function. One may then treat this $g(p(e_i), e_i)$ function as $p(e_i)$ in the usual MB extremization process.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, the key statistical idea is that $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ ((16)) for any $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. In other words, this represents minimal information which we suggest may be formulated in an extremization process. We suggest that the function to be extremized should provide no more information than a linear combination of the differentials of the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = e_{ave}$ ((17)). This leads to $\sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ being maximized with $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$.

In more complicated problems such as the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein cases, ((16)) does not hold, but one may consider the possibility of a dual space with $p(e_i)$ replaced with $g(p(e_i))$ for which one may apply the MB process to $g(p(e_i))$. In such a case, one has to know the form of $g(p(e_i))$ from physical considerations (i.e. reaction balance). In the FD case, $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))$ and in the BE, $p(e_i)/(1+p(e_i))$. We note that this dual space approach differs from the usual entropy density $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) - (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i))$ which is maximized with respect to the physical constraints ((17)). This dual space approach may also be applied to the gamma distribution which (1) proposes replaces the MB distribution, i.e $C (e/T)^{k-1} \exp(-e/T)$.

References

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